

**The specific problems of the recovery of
Historical architectural monuments of Kashkadarya region
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Abstract: In the article shows that It was found that there were several problems in the field of urban development practices aimed at preserving historical-architectural objects in the region in the first years of independence, that the master plans of the historical centers of ancient cities were not up to the required level, which caused distortions in their compositional-architectural appearance, and that the practice of eliminating these mistakes in the first years of independence was also not perfect, it is stated that practical works are being carried out in this field today.

Key words: Architectural monument, monument, object, palace, mosque, madrasa, caravanserai, toq, tim, chorsu, modern trade enterprises, shopping centers, shops, stalls.

Each architectural monument aims to enrich our understanding of the development of the culture of the peoples of a certain region, the construction method, and the intelligence of our ancestors [1:1492-1495]. Preservation of architectural monuments as they are depends not only on renovating them so that they are suitable for viewing, but also on reviving human contact with them, that is, adapting them to the types of services specific to the times.

Adaptation of architectural monuments to modern use primarily aims to preserve the monument and its spiritual essence almost unchanged must be kept [2:135-138]. Here, on the one hand, the main attention should be focused on preserving the original artistic expression, volume-spatial and plan structure (harmony) of the architectural monument, and on the other hand, it is necessary to focus on creating all the necessary conditions for the use of the monument as a "new" object. The main problem in this regard is to repair the monument, to correctly determine which type of the monument is suitable for modern services and which specific service it is suitable for. In this field, the scientific and practical experiences gained by the open joint-stock company "Uzbek timirshunoslik" for the repair and adaptation of architectural monuments of Uzbekistan in our Republic are especially worthy of attention. In it, several architectural monuments repair and adaptation projects in historical cities such as Ko'kan and Nurota were developed and implemented [3:1-6]. A number of recommendations related to the

repair, preservation and use of architectural monuments for modern purposes were developed and implemented at the institute.

In order to use the existing historical buildings for modern purposes, first of all, a project of adaptation of the historical monument to a new modern function should be developed. It is recommended that the adaptation of the obida to the new service function should be taken into account. First of all, it is necessary to determine what types of life services need to be organized in the environment where the architectural monument is located [4:96-100]. Then, thinking about which of these needs the primary functional essence of the monument, i.e. the building, the size plan compositional structure, and the architectural possibilities are most suitable for, which of these functions will be effective both for the monument and for urban planning and social life must be seen. In this case, the planning structure, design, style and interior appearance of the monument, the condition of preservation of the main devices serve as the determining conditions. The newly selected function should not have a negative impact on the architectural-planning structure of the building, it should be effective in maintaining the building in all aspects [5:121-123]. The new function should not harm the devices, artistic and historical social essence of the monument, internal and external environment of the building. Based on these requirements, the classification of adaptation of architectural monuments to modern purposes can be recommended as follows:

- hotels, company houses, dormitories, motels, campsites, tourist and adaptation to excursion destinations;
- trade facilities (toq, tim in turn modern trade) own business centers, stores, shops, stalls adaptation;
- adaptation of prayer buildings (mosques, minarets, mausoleums, shrines) to exhibition and exposition halls [7:128-132], houses of folk handicrafts, museums, and, if necessary, to return mosques and minarets to their functions;
- adaptation of palaces and fortifications, in turn, to tourist complexes, large museums, restaurants, kitchens, coffee houses, tea houses and similar institutions;
- adaptation of citezen buildings (bathrooms and other architectural and monuments) to separate service and health care institutions, baths, domestic service houses, exhibitions, sanatoriums

The proposed customization classification can be as broad as desired. Currently, many of the former mosques and mausoleums in the possession of the state have been returned to religious organizations. For example, Kokgumbaz mosque, Khojai Jarroh

mausoleum, Langar ata mosque and mausoleum in Qamashi, Sultan Mir Haydar complex in Kasbi, Shrine of Hazrat Bashir in Kitab [8] and others were returned to religious organizations. Perhaps the return of many monuments to the disposal of religious organizations will contribute to the preservation of architectural monuments. But architectural monuments with a high level of artistic and social significance, such as the Odina Mosque, Dor ut-Tilovat and Dor us-Saadat complex monuments, madrasahs are mainly used for spiritual purposes: national museums, residences, exhibitions or architectural spectacles, if they are used as open-air national theaters.

During the years of independence, many good deeds were done in Kashkadarya region in terms of preservation, repair and restoration of material cultural heritage objects and promotion of our great heritage, which proves our historical and cultural development of thousands of years, to our people, especially the young generation, as well as foreign guests, tourists, and the whole world. done. The 660th anniversary of Amir Temur and the 2700th anniversary of the cities of Karshi and Shahrisabz were widely celebrated internationally [9:59-63]. In the past years, Aksaroy, Doruttilovat, Dorussaodat complexes in Shahrisabz, Blue Dome, Kunduzak Mosque, Chubin Madrasa, Chorsu Trade Dome, Koba Caravanserai, Fortress Wall, Hazrat Imam, Abdishukur Ogalik, Khoja Murad Bakhshi, Khoja Isparos, Kunchiqar and Uychili Mosques, Gumbazi Sayyidon Tomb, Khoja Ilm Mining House, Odina in Karshi, Blue Dome Complexes , Sardoba, Abdulazizkhan, Bekmir madrasahs, Kashkadarya bridge, etc., large-scale repair, restoration and beautification works were carried out.

There is a passport of objects of material cultural heritage, which includes information on the content of protection of objects of material cultural heritage and a description of the object. However, most of the archeological objects have not been marked with a protection sign or a protection tag. According to the analysis, the conservation status of almost 15 percent of the tangible cultural heritage objects in the region is not documented. There is no single approach to protection signs installed on architectural objects. There are problems with the inclusion of tangible cultural heritage objects in the state cadastre.

During the years of independence, special attention was paid to restoration, study [10:73-76] and promotion of national and spiritual values in our country, preservation of cultural monuments, holy places, their restoration and repair based on established architectural requirements in accordance with their original appearance. extensive work was done. Many architectural monuments that were once abandoned have been restored.

However, our historical monuments are still waiting for the attention of the authorities, and are approaching the danger of collapse every year due to neglect and neglect [11:86-90]. One of them is from Guzor [14:292-296] district. It is an architectural monument of a tavern and a tower located in Khojaguzar neighborhood, on the Guzor-Dehkhanabad highway.

Today's demand is to restore and repair it in accordance with its original appearance, based on the established architectural requirements.

Based on this, the decision of the government dated November 11, 2013 "On the program for the development of the tourism industry in Kashkadarya region [12:386-391] in the period of 2013-2015" provides for the renovation of this architectural complex by September 2014, and the work in this regard is covered by the state budget. It was determined to be financed on the basis of funds[13:73-76]. But the planned work remained on paper. In this regard, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the republic was adopted, not of the district or regional governor, and special programs were drawn up, even though it was determined from where and how much money would be allocated, who was responsible, but its implementation was not ensured. So, the current state of most of the objects of material cultural heritage in Kashkadarya region is not commendable.

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